

In varietal screening trials against SR fungi, *Humicola* sp. was recorded on 54 entries. Nineteen varieties were most susceptible: Tadukan, M. sung song, Jhona 349, HKR207, HAU53-4618-2-1, HAU118-358, HAU120-326, HAU98-8, C-1321-9, C-1158-7, HAU10-194-1, HAU6-11-1-1-1-1, HAUS-145-1, HKR111, Pusa 33, IR29692-65-2-3, IR25861-35-3-3, IR25890-82-5-3, and IR13538-48-2-3-2. □

Association of SR fungi with wet culm crown rot at RRS, Kaul, India.

Category	Description	SR association (% tillers)			
		<i>S. oryzae</i>	<i>S. oryzae</i> var. <i>irregularare</i>	<i>S. hydrophilum</i>	<i>Humicola</i> sp.
1	Whole stool easily pulled out, breaking at crown, roots left inside soil	30	25	100	100
2	Partial stool pulled out	10	–	50	50
3	Stool pulled out with difficulty, roots intact	20	20	100	–

Acquired resistance of rice leaves to *Rhizoctonia solani*

K. Kalaiselvi, S. Sreenivasaprasad, and K. Manibhushanrao, Centre of Advanced Studies in Botany, University of Madras, A. C. College, Madras 600025, India

Sheath blight (ShB) incited by *Rhizoctonia solani* is a major fungal disease of rice. Acquisition of ShB resistance in excised rice leaves has been worked out through prior interaction with an avirulent *R. solani* isolate.

Several isolates from rice and other field crops were screened on TKM9 and Ponni for relative virulence. Avirulence on rice of isolate R7 from potato was further confirmed on CO 43 and IR50.

Leaves excised from 60-d-old field-grown rice plants were floated on 5 ppm kinetin to delay senescence and inoculated with a rice grain culture of R7. The leaves were challenged with sclerotia of virulent isolate R1 / R5 at 12 h. Disease spread was scored every 24 h from 48 h after challenge inoculation to 120 h.

In leaves preinoculated with R7, sclerotia of the virulent isolate did not spread until 72 h and formed only a few lesions, for 90% protection (see figure).

The generally slow-growing avirulent isolate R7 showed neither antibiosis nor parasitism and was overgrown by R5 in dual culture. Histopathological studies revealed sparse growth of R7 at the site of

Effect of incompatible interaction on ShB severity. DSI = av no. of lesions/leaf × av lesion length (cm).

inoculation, with inability to produce infection cushions on rice leaves. Direct penetration of the mycelium through either stomata or cuticle was not observed.

The fact that 60-65% protection against ShB could be obtained even when leaves were challenge-inoculated where R7 had not spread (2-3 cm

away) rules out direct antagonism between the 2 RS isolates and any competition for entry, colonization, and leaf exudates. Activation of host defense mechanisms might be responsible for acquired resistance. Preinoculation of rice leaves (prior-interaction) with R7 successfully induced protection. □